

6 5 4 3 2 1

D

Top View
Scale 1:15

Isometric View
Scale 1:15

C

Front View
Scale 1:15

Right Side View
Scale 1:15

B

A

D

C

B

A

UNLESS OTHERWISE SPECIFIED: DIMENSIONS ARE IN MILLIMETERS SURFACE FINISH: TOLERANCES: LINEAR: ANGULAR:			FINISH:			DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
All the dimensions are in mm.											
						Storage Unit Tray					
						Tray					
						A4					
						SCALE: 1:20					
						SHEET 1 OF 1					

6 5 4 3 2 1